

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West District

Jeasabelle A. Ramos¹, Agripina F. Banayo, Ed.D²

¹ Elementary Teacher I, Manggalang 1 Sariaya, Quezon, Philippines

² Instructor I, San Pablo City 4000, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The study aimed to determine the techniques and skills of supervisory leadership relative to teachers' motivation. The study used of descriptive method where questionnaire was the primary data gathering instrument. One hundred fifteen (115) Teachers from Sariaya West District contributed to the study. Frequency, percentage, mean, SD and Pearson r were used in the statistical analysis of data. The study revealed as perceived by the Teachers-respondents on School Head's Practice Techniques on Supervisory Leadership with regards to Consultative or Democratic Technique, Authoritarian or Dictatorial technique and non-interfering or Free-rein technique were found Evident. Likewise, rate of the school leaders often for level of Supervisory Leadership Skills in terms of Human Relation/ Interpersonal Skills, Conceptual and Technical: school head rate as Often in the Maslow's stages of motivational theory that affect teacher- respondents in terms Physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs and self- actualization. It was revealed that the techniques of supervisory leadership and motivation of teacher's respondents were related with one another, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the stated dependent variable and independent variable in the consultative and non-interfering techniques meanwhile Authoritarian technique is not supported by evidence hence it is not sustained.

KEYWORDS: Authoritarian, Consultative, Conceptual, Motivational theory, Supervisory Leadership

INTRODUCTION

Instructive supervision leading that is relevant viewpoints on conduct explains objectives and contributes to both encourages organizational actions, directions interactions, enables upkeep and improvement of the educational plan, and evaluates goal achievements.

Supervision is required for the teachers' professional development qualities. It can be said that educational supervision has the task of putting the current situation of educational administration forward, providing feedback on the operation of the system, proving assistance to schools and help for personal development to achieve the objects (Ministry of Education, 2001).

One significant development of teachers involves the method in which they are being evaluated, including the measures and tools that are used and provided by the Department of Education (DepEd).

The researcher pursues this study to determine the techniques and skills that are relevant to use by the respondents to motivate more to do their work well.

Rapid improvements in information technologies inevitably prompted substantial changes in education in the wake of the era of knowledge explosion. Changes of this nature increase the necessity for effective resource management in educational institutions, strong leadership, and the development of a skilled workforce in educational institutions. All of this necessitates extensive and ongoing educational institution supervision services to ensure the professional growth of teachers and other educational institution staff. As a result, supervision becomes the essential tool for ensuring quality and raising standards.

One of the duties and functions of an instructional supervisor, according to the Department of Education's Instructional Supervision: Standards, Procedures and Tools is a curricular enhancement, technical assistance, and assessment of learning outcomes. The instructional supervisor implements, monitors, supervise, and assesses the school curriculum to improve learning outcomes.

School heads have numerous roles to perform. Hauserman and Stick (2013) asserted that the function of the school head is the main factor in school efficiency since they make and keep up school development and improvement. They are implementer, evaluator of school programs, analyst of strategies and techniques, educator evaluator, plan setter, and delegator. They deal with other administrators, teachers, parents, and students. However, dealing, socializing, and communicating with them is different from the past experiences each one had. School heads continue to cope with changes in educational setting as a result of the pandemic,

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

as this situation has happened unexpectedly.

Background of the Study

The researcher observed in the supervisory leadership of the school head in their district, the school head used diverse type of supervision as their teachers needed. Some of the school head used different techniques and strategies in order to manage their subordinates. Being a leader is not an ordinary work. It needs focus on the progress of the school and a leader must assure that their subordinates have harmonious relationships with one another. If the school head knows the importance of every teacher the lather will be motivated to do their job well.

As stated in the Department of Education Instructional Supervision: Standards, procedures and Tools, one of the duties and responsibilities of an instructional supervisor focused on curricular enhancement, technical assistance and assessment of learning outcomes. Thus, the instructional supervisor implements, monitors, supervise and assesses the school curriculum to assure higher learning outcomes.

Teaching effectiveness plays an important role in teaching and learning process. An effective teacher does not create an image of the students rather help the students to create of their own understanding the problems of the students and helping them by making any subject interesting by controlling the class and by being fair with the students while dealing with them. Effective teachers are the most important factor contributing to student achievement

According to DiPaola& Wagner, 2018, on their second edition of *Improving Instruction Through Supervision, Evaluation, and Professional Development* they've maintain the conceptual framework while updating sections to provide the most recent research on instructional strategies that have the most promise of helping all students to learn.

The sudden change in the educational setting impacts the teachers and students. School head needs to be supportive to teachers even through communication. They can motivate teachers by giving them input about their work and furthermore empower them to communicate their sentiments in friendly association. Yet, on the off chance that insufficient communication exists instead of viable, it can bring about personal and expert disappointment and moreover lead to clashes between employees within the organization. Incapable communication diminishes work profitability. On the off chance that teachers do not know what is expected of them, motivation and the mental agreement can be appalling.

THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Supervision requires a set of techniques and skills because it involves not only the management of human resources but also the management and completion of tasks and achievement of targets.

Ugboka (2012) stated that the school principals are the management whose responsibility is to provide variety of supervision techniques for teachers to see the need for change, plan for change and practice new behavior for effective teaching and learning. Instructional supervision is the actions taken to mentor and monitor subordinates or teachers and provide supportive and conducive atmosphere for improvement on the instructional process. It requires planned and systematic monitoring of subordinates and providing professional guidance and assistance to them in order to ensure the successful implementation of the formal or informal curriculum in the school.

According to Oyewole and Ehinola, 2014, one of the important aspects of educational management is instructional supervision which may be defined as the process of bringing about improvement in the teaching-learning process through a network of cooperative activities and democratic relationship of persons concerned with teaching and learning, and it is considered as an important activity to achieve an effective education system).

Dr. Nazrul Islam (2021) anchored his *Techniques of Supervisory* into the *Leadership Styles* of Kurt Lewin (1930). According to him, using supervising techniques such as consultative or democratic technique, authoritarian or dictatorial technique and non-inter fearing or free-rein technique can help supervisors to manage employees successfully. Supervision requires a set of techniques and skills because it involves not only the management of human resources but also the management and completion of tasks and achievement of targets. Creating an effective method to supervise is important for achieving clarity and method at work.

While someone is being supervised, they are being given instructions, direction, oversight, and observation while carrying out tasks for the organization. It describes the workplace activities where a manager supervises the duties and responsibilities of the workers he manages. It is a crucial job responsibility for all managers inside your organization. A supervisor's typical duties include mentoring, training, and personnel development. Thus, a manager must ensure that all instructions are given to each and every employee.

The function of supervision guarantees strict control over the actions of subordinates. When employees are closely watched, they always use resources as efficiently as possible, which reduces waste. The supervisor's severe oversight and direction motivate the staff to exercise greater self-discipline in their work. The employees follow a set or rigid timetable and carry out the plans according to the supervisor's instructions. Supervisors provide a report on each employee's performance, which serves as the foundation for employee performance evaluations. The supervisor-employee connection is a very effective motivator to raise staff motivation levels. By directing the workers, the managers exhort the subordinates to meet their best capacity.

According to Robert Katz, there are critical skills sets for successful leaders: technical skills, interpersonal (or human) skills,

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

and conceptual skills. Leaders must possess certain technical skills that assist them in optimizing managerial performance. For Katz, technical skills are the broadest and most easily designed category. This is defined as a learned capacity in just about any given field of work.

An effective manager will have the leadership skills to paint a rich and vivid picture of what the future will look like once the vision is realized. Accelerate your career with award-winning courses and practice. Leadership entails more than just planning and sticking to it; you must also demonstrate proactive problem solving and the ability to look ahead. It's about never being satisfied with the status quo and always striving to improve, evolve, and deliver. Once the vision has been developed, it must be both compelling and convincing.

According to our innate and desires, Abraham Maslow's motivation theory (1943), often known as Maslow's hierarchy of needs, is a theoretical framework that describes the numerous motivations that humans experience. According to Maslow's theory the next level of requirements starts to motivate human once the first level, which starts with our physical needs like food and sleep, has been met. Understanding more about Maslow's theory of motivation can help human to meet needs, increase motivation and improve team motivation at work.

Maslow's motivation theory is a way of describing the various level of human needs, starting with the most basic needs, which are physiological needs, finishing with our final supposed needs, which is reaching our full potential. Abraham Maslow posited that human motivation arise out of motivation to progress through this hierarchy of needs. Maslow represented his theory pictorially as a pyramid, similar to the food pyramid, with the bottom representing the base and the most basic level. Once a person satisfies one level of needs, Maslow suggests to become motivated to reach the next level.

Maslow outlined the five stages of the theory. According to his theory, once human fulfill the requirements of the first level, human is driven to move on to the following level in a sequential manner. The levels that makes up Maslow's hierarchy of needs are as follows: physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization.

This presents the summary of readings on the significance and relationship of the subject under the study. Such reading provides insights serving as frames of references that help to conceptualize the study.

Table 1. Summary of Table on the Perception of the Respondents on Supervisory Techniques

Supervisory Techniques	Mean	SD	VI
Consultative/Democratic Technique	3.40	0.55	Evident
Authoritarian/Dictatorial Technique	2.74	0.81	Evident
Non-inter fearing/Free-Rein Technique	3.33	0.47	Evident
Overall	3.16	0.61	Evident

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Evident, 2.50-3.49 Evident, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Evident, 1.00-1.49 Not Evident

It is presented in table 1 that school heads were observed to used different techniques in supervising teachers. As we gleaned on the table, consultative or democratic technique got the highest mean of 3.40, SD of .55 and interpreted as evident. It indicates that teachers are motivated when school heads listened and accepted their opinions and suggestions with the different school matters. It denotes that teacher-respondents perceived the involvement of the subordinates in decision-making really matters and evident. It is the same in the study of Yukl (2009) and Warren Bennis (2018) that allows school leaders to set their sights on the goals with the involvement of the members of the groups. This was agreed by Daing and Dimaano (2015) and Sociology Guide (2022) which emphasized the influence of leadership towards achieving the goals being set. Permitting subordinates to share opinions about school matters will lead to harmonious relationship between the school head and with his subordinates.

Table 2. Summary of Table on the Perception of the Respondents on Supervisory Skills

Supervisory Skills	Mean	SD	VI
Human relations/interpersonal	3.38	0.56	Evident
Conceptual	3.38	0.57	Evident
Technical	3.39	0.55	Evident
Overall	3.38	0.56	Evident

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Evident, 2.50-3.49 Evident, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Evident, 1.00-1.49 Not Evident

As gleaned in table 2 the overall mean is 3.38 with standard deviation of 0.56 implies that the school heads are rendered diverse supervisory skills. School heads should have knowledge about different skills in supervising his subordinates. The table indicates that all the skills are essentials for school heads to manage teachers. Technical skills got the peak mean of 3.38, SD of 0.56 and interpreted as evident. This is aligned with the statement of Donkoh & Baffoe (2018) technical skills also refer to the specialized knowledge and skills needed to conduct supervision. These skills include the ability to use appropriate tools, procedures, or

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

techniques to carry out job-know-how work in specific fields which is agreed by Thakral (2015) that the academic aims of supervision include tasks such as: monitoring of instruction, guiding teachers to improvement the teaching and learning process, assessment of student's learning outcomes, evaluating goals of programs.

Table 3. Summary of Table on the Teacher-respondents Level of Motivation

Teachers' Motivation	Mean	SD	VI
Physiological Needs	3.32	0.52	Often
Safety Needs	3.33	0.54	Often
Social Needs	3.33	0.54	Often
Esteem Needs	3.43	0.61	Often
Self-Actualization Needs	3.44	0.55	Often
Overall	3.37	0.55	Often

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Always, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 1.50-2.49 Often, 1.00-1.49 Never

Table 3 shows the summary of teacher-respondents level of motivation with regards to physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization needs. It has an overall mean of 3.37, with SD of 0.55 and interpreted as often. It indicates that it is very essentials that school heads help teachers to fulfil those needs and it will motivate them to do their job very well. Self-actualization had the highest mean of 3.44, SD of 0.55 and often for verbal interpretation. The results emphasize that School leaders must be the channel of new knowledge and understanding which links to self-realization that targets the goal of the organization for the welfare of the body. Voegtlin et al., (2012) and Antunes and Franco (2016) suggest from their studies that responsible leadership is a conduct, which aims to promote open interaction and communication between parties continuously and frequently to build mutually beneficial relationships. Interaction is the daily practice of leaders to be involved in communication engagement with their subordinates (Voegtlin et al, 2012). Harmonious communication and relationships achieved through self-realization in achieving the goals of the organization. Self-actualization is translated as the full realization of someone's potential or true self.

The examples of self-actualization may vary, like expressing their creativity, a journey for spiritual enlightenment, or pursuit of knowledge. This implies that when the leaders are harmoniously practicing the self-realization strategy will lead to a successful good outcome from the group.

Table 4: Relationship between the techniques and skills of supervisory leadership and motivation of the teacher-respondent

Supervisory Leadership		Teacher Motivation				
		physiological	safety	social	esteem	self
Techniques	Consultative	.616**	.717**	.748**	.751**	.787**
	Authoritarian	0.149	0.139	0.051	0.062	0.122
	Non-interfering	.657**	.765**	.718**	.707**	.702**
Skills	Human relations	.764**	.842**	.873**	.827**	.816**
	Conceptual	.776**	.848**	.816**	.846**	.838**
	Technical	.758**	.829**	.749**	.754**	.775**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 shows that there are significant relationships between consultative leadership and teachers' motivation in terms of physiological needs ($r=.616^{**}$), safety needs ($r=.717^{**}$), social needs ($r=.751^{**}$), esteem needs ($r=.751^{**}$) and self-actualization ($r=.787^{**}$). It means that the school heads use consultative or democratic leadership, the teachers are motivated to do their job very well. School administration should be able to utilize its leadership qualities effectively to motivate teachers, unite them around organizational goals and, most importantly, to improve education training (Kalkan&Karadag,2020).This indicates that school leaders must sustain with the consultative techniques since it was found out that it is important and relevant to the motivation of teachers which give a good performance seen in their work output and provide a harmonious relationship with the organization. Giving chance to raise opinions and suggestions really matters to teachers because it will help to boost teacher's self-esteem. Teachers are motivated to work hard when school heads appreciate the work they do.

On other hand, authoritarian leadership does not have a significant positive correlation with teachers' motivation in terms of physiological needs (0.149), safety needs (0.139), social needs (0.51), esteem needs (0.062) and self-actualization (0.122). Wang H. & Guan B.,2018, gave some characteristics of authoritarian leadership that maybe the reasons why respondents didn't feel motivated if their school head is an autocratic leader.

Some of the primary characteristics of autocratic leadership include:

- Allows little or no input from group members

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

- Requires leaders to make almost all of the decisions
- Provides leaders with the ability to dictate work methods and processes
- Leaves the group feeling like they aren't trusted with decisions or important tasks
- Tends to create highly structured and very rigid environments
- Discourages creativity and out-of-the-box thinking
- Establishes rules and tends to be clearly outlined and communicated

Non-interfering technique has positive correlations with all types of teacher motivation in terms of physiological needs ($r=0.657^{**}$), safety needs ($r=0.765^{**}$), social needs ($r=0.718^{**}$), esteem needs ($r=0.707^{**}$) and self-actualization ($r=0.702^{**}$). Overall, the results suggest that different techniques of supervisory leadership may have varying levels of influence on different types of teacher motivation. This indicates that school leaders must give focus on how to give time on improving the authoritarian techniques in leadership. Consultative techniques appear to have stronger positive relationships with teacher motivation than authoritarian or non-interfering leadership techniques.

In the study of Tekin (2019) the above results are found relevant as being mentioned about motivation affects the morale of employees, attitudes, and behaviors towards the organization. It is said to be an important factor in succeeding individual and structural goals. Directing individuals with different characteristics to unite around a common goal and achieve success within an organization is only possible if the employees are properly coordinated and motivated by the manager. The main factors that positively affect teachers' motivation are the management practices in schools that include individuals with different characteristics.

It is also shown on table 13 that there is significant correlation between human relations with teachers' motivation variables in terms of physiological needs ($r=0.764^{**}$), safety needs ($r=0.842^{**}$), social needs ($r=0.873^{**}$), esteem needs ($r=0.827^{**}$) and self-actualization ($r=0.816^{**}$). It means that having human relations skills of school head over his subordinates is very essential for the motivation of the teachers to feel that the latter are treated appropriately. We can glean also from table 14 that having conceptual skills of school head has significant correlation with teachers' motivation in terms of physiological needs ($r=0.776^{**}$), safety needs ($r=0.848^{**}$), social needs ($r=0.816^{**}$), esteem needs ($r=0.846^{**}$) and self-actualization ($r=0.838^{**}$). Conceptual skills are very important skills that school heads should have because a leader needs to have some concepts for any situations that the school may encounter to sustain the orderliness in the school. Technical skills found also have significant correlation with teachers' motivation in terms of physiological needs ($r=0.758^{**}$), safety needs ($r=0.829^{**}$), social needs ($r=0.749^{**}$), esteem needs ($r=0.754^{**}$) and self-actualization ($r=0.775^{**}$). Having technical skills is essential for the school head for the leading and coaching his employees.

In addition, which is found the same in the study Kayhan (2010) stressed that principal of the school who takes duty by appointment is the administrator who receives power from legal, social, and technical powers. The school principal takes them legal authority from the authority they hold, social powers from the staff and environment they work in, and their technical powers from their knowledge and management skills.

The school leaders are expected to have all these powers to be an effective leader. Furthermore, they must have some other characteristics to perform their duties successfully. One of the most prominent of these is leadership skills. School administration should be able to utilize its leadership qualities effectively to motivate teachers, unite them around organizational goals and, most importantly, to improve education training (Kalkan&Karadag,2020).

Since it was revealed that the techniques of supervisory leadership and motivation of teacher's respondents were related with one another, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the stated dependent variable and independent variable in the consultative and non-interfering techniques meanwhile Authoritarian technique is not supported by evidence hence it is not sustained.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the study conducted. This also presents the findings derived from the analysis and interpretation of the results. Moreover, this imparts the conclusions framed and the recommendations formulated thereafter.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The study sought to determine the techniques and skills of supervisory leadership relative to teachers' motivation. Based on the data gathered, the following findings were summarized:

1. School Head's Techniques on Supervisory Leadership with regards to Consultative or Democratic Technique got the mean of (3.40) and SD of (0.55), Authoritarian or Dictatorial technique got mean (2.74) SD (0.81) and non-inter fearing or Free-rein technique obtained mean of (3.33) and SD (0.47) which all of them interpretation was Evident.
2. The surveyed respondents rate Often for the level of Supervisory Leadership Skills described by the teacher-respondents in terms of Human Relation/ Interpersonal Skills with the mean of (3.38) SD (0.56), Conceptual got mean of (3.38) SD (0.57) and lastly in Technical which obtained the mean of (3.39) SD (0.55).
3. The surveyed respondents rate the school heads Evident for the Maslow's stages of motivational theory that affect teacher-respondents in terms Physiological needs with the mean of (3.32) SD (0.52), safety needs got the mean of (3.33) SD (0.54), social

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

needs obtained mean of (3.33) SD (0.54), esteem needs had mean of (3.43) SD (0.52) and self- actualization with mean (3.44) and SD of (0.55).

4. There is positive relationship between consultative leadership and teachers' motivation.
5. There is positive relationship between non-inter fearing leadership technique and teachers' motivation.
6. There is no significant relationship between authoritarian leadership techniques and teachers' motivation.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the following conclusion:

1. It was revealed that the techniques of supervisory leadership and motivation of teacher's respondents were related with one another, the hypothesis stating that there is significant relationship between the stated dependent variable and independent variable in the consultative and non-interfering techniques meanwhile Authoritarian technique is not supported by evidence hence it is not sustained.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The school administration may continue the programs or Seminar Workshop before each school year to maintain the empowerment of school leaders and teachers in the proper knowledge on practice with the techniques of supervisory leadership in Consultative, Authoritarian and Non-interfering since it is already found evident.
2. School leaders with teachers may continue the mentoring session about proper knowledge or practice the techniques on supervisory leadership in Consultative, Authoritarian and Non-interfering and be aware with the Maslow's stages of motivational theory in the physiological needs, safety need, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization to increase positive working environment in the school.
3. May conduct a parallel study through Action Research to show the evident of techniques and skills of supervisory leadership with regards to Consultative, Authoritarian and Non-interfering relative to teachers' motivation; the physiological needs, safety need, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization that already often observed by the respondents.
4. School leaders may continue promoting daily activities for the teachers' welfare that involve techniques and skills of supervisory leadership with regards to Consultative, Authoritarian and Non-interfering relative to teachers' motivation which involves the Physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, and self- actualization.
5. Attend workshop that will sustain the techniques and skills of supervisory leadership with regards to Consultative, Authoritarian and Non-interfering relative to teachers' motivation which involves the Physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, and self-actualization that had been observed by the respondents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher would like to extend her grateful appreciation in the preparation and completion of her research study. This study would not have been completed without the support, help and priceless contributions of the persons close to her heart.

REFERENCES

- 1) Amanchukwu, RN,et.al. (2015), A Review of leadership Theories, Principles and Styles and Their Relevance to Educational Management.
- 2) Anderson, R. C. (1959). Learning in discussions: A resume of the authoritarian-democratic studies. *Harvard Educational Review*, 29, 201-212
- 3) Anthony et al., (2007). Health and Safety Needs. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 4) Antunes, A., & Franco, M. (2016). How people in organizations make sense of responsible leadership practices: Multiple case studies. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 37(1), 126–152
- 5) Arifin, N. (2012), Analysis of the quality of working life, performance and job satisfaction in CV duta senenan jepara. *Journal Economica*, 8(1), 11-21
- 6) Ayeni (2012). Principals' Instructional Time management and students' academic performance. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 7) Bambacas and Patrickson (2008). Collaborative Decision making. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 8) Bhandari (2021). Correlational Design. Retrieved November 12,2021 from www.google.com
- 9) Barman, J. (2022) Employee Promotion: The Types, Benefits, & Whom to Promote
- 10) Bass, B. M. (1990). *Bass & Stogdill's handbook of leadership: Theory, research & managerial applications* (3rd ed.). New York: *Free Press*

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

- 11) Bailey, J.R. & Rehman, S. (2022). Don't Underestimate the Power of Self-Reflection. *Harvard Business Review – Ascend*. <https://hbr.org/2022/03/dont-underestimate-the-power-of-self-reflection>
- 12) Bidee, et al. (2017). Psychological Needs. Retrieved November 12, 2021 from www.google.com
- 13) Bolger, N., and Laurenceau, J.-P. (2013). *Intensive Longitudinal Methods: Introduction to Diary and Experience Sampling Research*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- 14) Bolger, K.E., & Patterson, C.J. (2001). Pathways from child maltreatment to internalizing problems: Perceptions of control as mediators and moderators. *Development and Psychopathology*, 13, 913-940. Retrieved November 12, 2021 from www.google.com
- 15) Buote et al. (2007). Age Graded Differences. Retrieved November 12, 2021 from www.google.com
- 16) Ceri-Booms, M. (2010). An empirical study on transactional and authentic leaders: Exploring the mediating role of trust in the leader on organizational identification. *The Business Review*, 14(2), 235-243. Retrieved from http://search.proquest.com.ezproxy.apollolibrary.com/docview/3475654_87?accountid=35812
- 17) Cellar, D.F., Sidle, S., Goudy, K., O'Brien, D. 2001. Effects of leader style, leader sex, and subordinate personality on leader evaluations and future subordinate motivation. *J. Bus. Psychol.* 16, 1 (Fall 2001), 61-72. DOI= 10.1023/A:1007887721571
- 18) Çetinkanat, C. & Sağnak, M. (2010). Preferences of teachers in primary schools regarding their supervisory style. 2nd National Educational Supervision Symposium with International Participation. (pp. 85-93) Kutahya: Dumlupınar University.
- 19) Chiovere (2014). Assesment of Implementaion on Supervision. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 20) Crehan, L.; Tournier, B.; Chimier, C.; 2019. *Teacher career pathways in New York City*. Paris: IIEP-UNESCO
- 21) Cunningham, J., et al (2015). Project management leadership style: a team member perspective. *Int. J. Glob. Bus.* 8, 2 (Dec. 2015), 27-54.
- 22) Daing and Dimaano (2015). School Administrators' Instructional Leadership Skills and Teachers Performance. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 23) Danish, R. Q., & Usman, A. (2010). Impact of reward and recognition on job satisfaction and motivation: An empirical study from Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(2), P159.
- 24) Dawley, D.D., Stephens, R.D. and Stephens, D.B. (2005), "Dimensionality of organizational commitment in volunteer workers: chamber of commerce board members and role fulfillment", *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 67 No. 3, pp. 511-525.
- 25) Dea, M. (2016). *The Nexus between Instructional Supervision, Supervisors' and Teachers': The Practical Paradox and Its Effect on Quality Education*
- 26) Deci, E. L., and Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychol. Inq.* 11, 227–268. doi: 10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- 27) Decoene and Bruggeman (2006). Model of Relationship between strategic alignment, motivation and Organizational Performance. Retrieved February 30, 2020 from www.google.com
- 28) Den and Verburg (2004). Impact of High Performing Work System. Retrieved February 30, 2020 from www.google.com
- 29) Denhardt, J. V., & Denhardt, R. B. (2003). *The new public service: Serving, not steering*. Armonk, NY: M. E. Sharpe
- 30) DiPaola and Wagner (2018). *Improving Instruction Through Supervision, Evaluation, and Professional Development*. Retrieved February 30, 2020 from www.google.com
- 31) Donkoh, E., & Baffoe, S. (2018). Instructional Supervisory Practices of Headteachers and Teacher Motivation in Public Basic Schools in Anomabo Education Circuit. *Journal of Education and e- Learning Research*, 5(1), 43-50. Retrieved from <http://birbhum.gov.in/DPSC/reference/91.pdf>
- 32) Drew, C. (April 21, 2022). 18 Physiological Needs Examples (Maslow's Hierarchy). Helpful Professor. <https://helpfulprofessor.com/physiological-needs-examples/>
- 33) Drummer, J., Hakimov, G., Joldoshev, M., Köhler, T., & Udartseva, S. (2018). Vocational Teacher Education in Central Asia Developing Skills and Facilitating Success
- 34) Durotulo (2002). Supervision Guidance. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 35) Ertanto, Y.D., Suharnomo, S. (2011), Effect of Salary on Employee Performance With Self Esteem as Intervening Variable (Studies in PDAM Grobogan). Thesis of Social Sciences UNDIP
- 36) Farber, B. A., & Hazanov, V. 2014. Informal Sources of Supervision in Clinical Training. *Journal of clinical psychology*, 70(11), 1062-1072.
- 37) Fiaz, M., Su, Q. and Ikram, A. (2017), "Leadership Styles and Employees' Motivation: perspective from an emerging economy", *The Journal of developing Areas*, Vol.51 No.4, pp.143-156
- 38) Garci-Herrero et al (2012). Health and safety Needs. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

- 39) Guay, F., Vallerand, R. and Blanchard, C. (2010) On the Assessment of Situational Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation: The Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS)
- 40) Gureckis, T. M., & Markant, D. (2012). Self-Directed Learning: A Cognitive and Computational Perspective. In *Perspectives on Psychological Science: A Journal of the Association for Psychological Science*, 7(5), 464-481. doi: 10.1177/1745691612454304
- 41) Hackman, M. Z., & Johnson, C. E. (1996). *Leadership: A communication perspective* (2nd ed.). Prospect Heights, IL: Waveland Press
- 42) Hagemann (2009). Technical and Interpersonal skills. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 43) Haryati, M.A. (2012), Quality of Work Life Relationship with Performance Implementing Nurse at Hospital Bali MED Denpasar. Thesis Pasca Sarjana FEUI Jakarta
- 44) Hauserman and Stick (2013). Numerous Roles of school Heads. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 45) Hersey, et.al (2001). Organizational Success and Problem Solving. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 46) Holt-Lunstad et al. (2015). Negative Health Influences. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 47) Hoque, K. E., Alam, G. M., & Abdullah A. G. K. (2010). Impact of teacher professional development on school improvement an analysis at Bangladesh standpoint. *Asia Pacific Education Review*. doi:10.1007/12564-010- 9107-Z
- 48) Honneth, A., (1997), *La lucha por el reconocimiento*, Spanish translation by Manuel Ballester, Barcelona, Crítica (cited as LpR). International Labour Organization (ILO) (1996-2022), retrieved from google
- 49) İnandi, Y., Uzun, A., Yeşil, H. 2016. The relationship between the principals' leadership styles and their efficacy in change management. *J. Educ. Sci. Res.* 6, 1 (Apr. 2016), 191-209. DOI= 10.12973/jesr.2016.61.10.
- 50) Iqbal, S. (2013), *Labour Fate: Diluting Inequality*. Jakarta: Kompas
- 51) Islam, N. (2021), *Techniques of Supervisory*. Retrieved from google.com
- 52) Ismil, A., Mohamed, H. A., Sulaiman, A. Z., Mohamad, M. H., & Yusuf, M. H., (2011), An empirical study of the relationship between transformational leadership, empowerment and organizational commitment. *Business and Economics Research Journal*, 2(1), 89-107. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com>. [ezproxy.apollolibrary.com /docview /847324928 ?accountid=35812](http://ezproxy.apollolibrary.com/docview/847324928?accountid=35812)
- 53) Investopedia, LLC (2018). *Developing Leaders*. Retrieved November 12, 2022 from www.google.com
- 54) James, F., & Massiah, A. (2019), Using clinical supervision as a professional development mechanism: Capabilities, concerns and challenges [Paper presentation]. A paper presented in ECER 2019 organized by European Educational Research Association. [https://eera-ecer.de/ecer-programmes/ conference/24/contribution/47916/](https://eera-ecer.de/ecer-programmes/conference/24/contribution/47916/)
- 55) Kalkan, Ü.; Altınay Aksal, F.; Altınay Gazi, Z.; Atasoy, R.; Dağlı, G. (2020). The relationship between school administrators' leadership styles, school culture, and organizational image. *Sage Open* 2020, 1–15. [CrossRef]
- 56) Kanzunnudin, M. (2007), Effect of wages and supervision of employee productivity: A case Study on PT Tonga Tiur Son Zenith District Kragan. *Fokus Ekonomi*, 2(1), 11-20.
- 57) Karadağ, M.; Altınay Aksal, F.; Altınay Gazi, Z.; Dağlı, G. (2020). Effect size of spiritual leadership: In the process of school culture and academic success. *Sage Open* 2020, 1–14. [CrossRef]
- 58) Karwati, W. (2019). Teacher Sdn Santaka Sub-District Cimanggung in Implementing Standards Process. *Pedagogic Journal of Basic Education*, 6(1), 41–9
- 59) Katz, R. (1973) *management skills pdf - Canadian Guidelines Step-by-step*. robcody.com/robert-katz-management-skills-pdf/
- 60) Kayhan, Ü.; Eroğlu, G. (2010). *School as an Educational Environment, Structure, Functioning and Relationships*; Damga Yayinevi: Ankara, Turkey
- 61) Khan, and Akkas, (1990; Kokemuller, (2013) retrieved from google
- 62) Kraiger, K., & Kirkpatrick, S., 2010. An empirical evaluation of three popular training programs to improve interpersonal skills. *Journal of Psychological Issues in Organizational Culture*, 1(1), 60-73. doi:10.1002/jpoc
- 63) Kunz and Pfaff. (2002). Effect of Extrinsic rewards on Intrinsic Motivation. Retrieved February 30, 2020 from www.google.com
- 64) *Leadership, Leadership Techniques* (sociologyguide.com)
- 65) Lewin, K. (1939). The consequences of an authoritarian and democratic leadership. In A. W. Gouldner, *Studies in leadership: Leadership and democratic action* (pp. 409-417). New York: Russell & Russell.
- 66) L. Lusiana and A. Nurabadi, (2018), Hubungan Pelaksanaan Supervisi Kolegial Dengan Kinerja Guru Pada Sekolah Dasar
- 67) Lindenberg (2013). Social Needs. Retrieved February 30, 2020 from www.google.com
- 68) M. D. Wibawa, (2019) "Meningkatkan Kinerja Guru dalam Menyusun Silabus dan Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran (RPP) melalui Supervisi Kolegial," *J. Educ. Action Res.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 66–71

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

- 69) Marquis, B.L., and Huston, C.J. (2017). Leadership Roles and Management Functions in Nursing: Theory and Application. (9theds) Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, Philadelphia.
- 70) Matias and Luistro (2011). The Supervisory Skills in Public Elementary School Principals. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google scholar.com
- 71) .Maloş, R. 2012. Leadership styles. Annals of EftimieMurgu University Resita Fascicle II, Economic Studies. 421-426.
- 72) McCombes (Revised 2020). Descriptive Research. Retrieved November 12,2021 from www.google scholar.com
- 73) Miller, D. 2018. "The Importance of Teacher Wellness".
- 74) Ministry of Education (2001). Framework for the curriculum reform of basic education (Trial Version). Ministry of Education.
- 75) Morrow, P. (2011), "Managing organizational commitment: insights from longitudinal research", Journal of Vocational Behavior, Vol. 79 No. 1, pp. 18-35.
- 76) Mitchell, G. W., Skinner, L. B., & White, B. J., 2010. Essential soft skills for success in the twenty-first-century workforce as perceived by business educators. Delta Phi Epsilon, 52(1), 4353. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com>. 50
- 77) Nayak, S.R., Patra, S. (2013), Wage-labour productivity relationship in manufacturing sector of Odisha: An observed analysis. International Journal of Engineering Science Invention, 2(3), 8-11.
- 78) Nayan, S., Shafie, L. A., Mansor, M., Maesin, A., & Osman, N., (2010), The practice of collaborative learning among lecturers in Malaysia. Management Science and Engineering, 4(2), 115123. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com.ezproxy.apollolibrary.com>.
- 79) Nelson, D. and J. Quick, (2012), Organizational behavior: Science, the real world, and you. 8th Edn., Ohio, OH: Cengage Learning.
- 80) NSLS, (2022). Key Characteristics of Democratic Leadership
- 81) Orodho and Waweru (2013), Retrieved from The Influence of Working Condition on Teacher's Job Satisfaction: the Case of Kisarawe District Public Secondary Teachers, Tanzania (Page 49-54)
- 82) Oyewole and Ehinola, (2014). Important Aspects of Educational Management. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google scholar.com
- 83) Pajak, E. (2010). The history and future of instructional supervision in the United States. 2. Uluslararası Katılımlı Ulusal Eğitim Denetimi Kongresi (pp. 1-19). York Kütahya: Dumlupınar Üniversitesi
- 84) Petrou, P., Bakker, A. B., Op den Kamp, E. M., & Tims, M. (2020). Proactive vitality management, work engagement, and creativity: The role of goal orientation. Applied Psychology: An International Review, 69(2), 351–378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12173>
- 85) Pinder, C.C., 2014. Work motivation in organizational behavior. 2nd Edn., New: Taylor & Francis.
- 86) Qasim (2010). The Effectiveness of Blended Learning in Improving Students Achievement. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google scholar.com
- 87) Robbins, S. P. 2007. Management Ninth Edition. New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- 88) Sauer, S.J. 2011. Taking the reins: the effects of new leader status and leadership style on team performance. J. Appl. Psychol. 96, 3 (May 2011), 574-587. DOI= 10.1037/a0022741.
- 89) Selvia. (2015). Implementasi supervisi akademik kepala sekolah dalam peningkatan profesionalisme guru. Manajer Pendidikan, 9(21), 43–49.
- 90) Sergiovanni and Starrat (2002). Educational leadership and management: Theory, Policy and Practice. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google scholar.com
- 91) Shafie, et.al (2010). Corporate Leaders Practice of interpersonal skills. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google scholar.com
- 92) Sias, Patricia M.; Gallagher, Erin B.; Kopaneva, Irina; Pedersen, Hannah (2011). "Maintaining Workplace Friendships". Communication Research. 39 (2): 239–268. doi:10.1177/0093650210396869. S2CID 26155388.
- 93) Sociology Guide.com (2022)
- 94) Souders, B. (2020). What is Motivation? A Psychologist Explains. Retrieved September 02, 2020 from positivepsychology.com
- 95) Stogdill, R. M. (1974). Handbook of leadership: A survey of theory and research. New York: Free Press
- 96) Tampam (2016). Purpose of supervision. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google scholar.com
- 97) Tekin, T. (2019). The Relationship between Initiative Levels and Problem-Solving Skills of School Administrators. Master's Thesis, Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi, Tokat, Turkey Available online: <https://tez.yok.gov.tr/UlusalTezMerkezi> (accessed on 3 August 2020)
- 98) Thakral, S. 2015. The historical context of modern concept of supervision. Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies, 6(1), 79-88.

Techniques and Skills on Supervisory Leadership Relative to Teachers' Motivation in Sariaya West Distric

- 99) Ugboka, F.E. (2012). A study of principals' supervisory strategies and secondary discipline. *C cJournal of Education and Social Research*, 2(1), 41-49.
- 100) Umar, A. (2012), Effect of wages, motivation, and job satisfaction on the performance of workers in the manufacturing industry in the city of Makassar. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 10(2), 406-418
- 101) Wang, H. Guan, B., (2018). The positive effect of authoritarian leadership on employee performance: The moderating role of power distance. *Front Psychol.*2018;9:357. Doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00357
- 102) Vansteenkiste et al.(2020). Basic psychological needs. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 103) Vidic, Z. and Burton, D. (2011), "Developing effective leaders: motivational correlates of leadership styles", *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, Vol. 23 No. 3, pp. 277-291.
- 104) Vroom, V. (1964). *Work and motivation*. New York: Wiley. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 105) Vuori and Okkonen. (2012). Intra-organizational platform. Retrieved February 30,2020 from www.google.com
- 106) Wanzare (2013). Skills and Attributes of Instructional Supervisors. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 107) Warren, Bennis (2018), *The Difference Between Management and Leadership*. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 108) Weinstein, (2013). Self-Actualization. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 109) Woliat Zone Administration Elementary and Secondary Schools (1-8). *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(7), 108-118. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1095254.pdf>
- 110) Wasserman T, Wasserman L (2020). "Motivation: State, Trait, or Both". *Motivation, Effort, and the Neural Network Model*. pp. 93–101. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 111) Woliat Zone Administration Elementary and Secondary Schools (1-8). *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(7), 108-118. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1095254.pdf>. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 112) Wu, C., Wang, P., & Tsai, L., 2010. The effect of organizational culture on team interaction and team effectiveness: Team leadership as a medium. *Journal of International Management Studies*, 5(2), 190-198. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com.ezproxy.apollolibrary.com.View>
- 113) Yesil. et.al (2016). The Impact of Cultural Intelligence on Cross-cultural Job Satisfaction and International Related Performance. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 114) Yeung, F. (2022), *Employsure, Employee Confidence Workplace Hygiene / Work Health & Safety / Employsure Blog*
- 115) Yukl, Gary (2009). *Leadership in Organizations*. Retrieved November 12,2022 from www.google.com
- 116) Zepeda (2003). *Formative Supervision*. Retrieved February 30,2020 from www.google.com